

Rayo's style Functions

SpF(n)

SpF(n)= the largest finite number that can be assigned to variable x defined with n characters that uses proper grammar and or math and or and all science which can't contain this same definition again Rayo's function can't be used if any special functions are used they must be defined.

ESpF(n)

ESpF(n)= the largest finite number that can be assigned to variable x defined with n characters that uses proper grammar and or math and or and all science which can't contain this same definition again values can contain rayo's function if any special functions are used they must be defined.

FSpF(n)

FSpF(n)= the largest cardinality number that can be assigned to variable x defined with n characters that uses proper grammar and or math and or and all science which can't contain this same definition again if any special functions are used they must be defined.